

Food system transformation potential of house gardening in the European Union – quantifying potential environmental benefits with hybrid Life Cycle Assessment

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Materials and Methods

Garden area

OSM maps garden area

Location of house gardens is not yet systematically mapped across Europe. Although OpenStreetMap (OSM) contains a layer with gardens, their mapping is not yet consistent and only a small fraction of gardens is actually indicated. Therefore, we developed a model based on other available information (layers) in the OSM. Our study covers the EU27 countries. Since we consider only house gardens in residential areas, the basis for our garden maps is the *landuse=residential* layer. However, large parts of residential areas are taken up by buildings, roads etc., which cannot be used for gardening. Thus, we removed all those areas from the layers. We downloaded (July 2024) OSM data from geofabrik (<https://download.geofabrik.de/>) with the resolution of individual countries or country regions in case of large countries like France or Germany. The maps were further processed in QGIS software. First, the *landuse* layer was filtered to contain only the polygons tagged as residential areas. To exclude all areas which are not used for habitation, such as industrial areas, commercial areas etc., the Difference process was used to delete all such specific *landuse* areas from the residential area. Next, all

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buildings (indicated in the *buildings* layer) were removed from the map, including a buffer around the buildings of approx. a meter. Furthermore, all *roads* were removed from the map using the Difference process, again with a buffer from the roads of approx. a meter. Finally, all the areas indicated in the *traffic* layer, places of worship (*pofw*) layer, and water layer were removed from the garden maps. This results in a map of areas which could be potentially used for house gardening (Fig 1.). The accuracy of the map varies with the OSM data detail. While in some countries and cities the OSM provides highly detailed information, in some countries and in smaller towns and villages, the accuracy and detail of the data is limited.

Figure 1 Example of the garden extent maps derived from the OSM data. Resulting garden areas indicated in green on the background of the OpenStreetMap. Randomly selected towns in a) Czech Republic, b) Belgium, c) France, Alsace, d) Italy, Centro.

Regression model for missing data

In several countries, the lack of detail in the OSM data prohibits the above-described approach. We used linear regression to approximate garden areas in those countries (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Malta, Spain, Portugal, and Romania) based on the countries for which more detailed data are available. Each polygon in the maps was assigned information on the modelled garden area, residential area indicated in the OSM layer, latitude, longitude, climatic zone (based on FAO GAEZ (Fischer, Nachtergaele et al. 2021)), mean annual precipitation, GDP (on

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the country or region level), population density (on the country or region level), and region (Europe divided in seven regions based on World Factbook categorization https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Regions_of_Europe). The linear regression models were developed using R (R Core Team 2024). The best models were selected based on Akaike Information Criterion. The resulting equations were used to derive garden areas in QGIS. The uncertainty of these derived values is presumably high.

Gardening yield and production

House gardening can comprise a wide range of practices and approaches, with varying crops, cultivation intensity, with different motivations, and in different conditions. Since our goal is to quantify the potential, rather than capture a current situation, we base our calculation on Agro-climatic potential yield values provided in the GAEZ database by FAO (Fischer, Nachtergaele et al. 2021). We selected (considering data availability) six vegetable crops as archetypical representatives of the wide variety of plants grown in house gardens: bean, cabbage, carrot, onion, potato, and tomato. The agro-climatic potential yield (kg DW per hectare per year) data are available as rasters at 5 arc-minute resolution. As the baseline scenario we used the historical data, time period of 1980-2010. The model allows to differentiate between cultivation with low or high nutrient input and between rainfed and irrigated. Using QGIS, we sampled the mean yield for each polygon and each crop, with low-input rainfed production taken as the bottom value and high-input irrigated value as the top value. Potential crop production for each of the scenarios was calculated as yield multiplied by garden area.

Gardening environmental impacts

Cultivation of crops in house gardens requires multiple steps and processes coupled with environmental impacts, such as production of seeds, fertilizers, or irrigation. The way we calculated those impacts is described in the following paragraphs. There are also several activities and impacts which, from some perspective, could be attributed to house gardening which we decided to exclude from our analysis. Among those are garden infrastructure (such as footpaths etc.) or gardening tools production. We believe it can be reasonably assumed that footpaths and other such infrastructure would be present (albeit in potentially different forms) even without cultivation. We also excluded the production of gardening tools from the analysis.

Seeds

One of the necessary inputs for gardening is seeds. The assumed seed or seedling requirements

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were based on information available in the FAO crop information database (<https://www.fao.org/land-water/databases-and-software/crop-information/en/>). We assumed that the planting density is fixed depending on area, without regard to actual yield (i.e., the same number of seeds or seedlings are planted per m² each year, even though the actual yield might differ depending on year, location and other factors). The life-cycle environmental impacts of seed and seedling production are based on Agribalyse 3.1.1. (Colomb, Amar et al. 2014) and ecoinvent 3.10 (Wernet, Bauer et al. 2016) data. Nevertheless, the practice of gardeners can vary, while some gardeners buy seeds or seedlings every year, many collect their own from the previous year's harvest or exchange with other gardeners. Therefore, we take the seed use to vary from zero (representing self-supplied seeds) to the maximum value described above.

Fertilizers

We took the maximum value of fertilizer demand for each crop from the Methodological guidance document for fertilizer use by the Czech Central Institute for Supervising and Testing in Agriculture (UKZUZ 2020). This document provides fertilizer needs per area for ideal soil nutrient content for each specific crop and different cultivation systems. The life cycle environmental impacts of fertilizer production (N, P, and K) were based on the ecoinvent (Wernet, Bauer et al. 2016) database. Again, many gardeners do not use mineral fertilizers, but rather they apply compost and other organic fertilizers. Therefore, the fertilizer demand in our analysis varies from zero (representing alternative or no fertilization) to the above-described values.

Irrigation

Irrigation demand for each crop is based on crop summary tables from the FAO GAEZ database (Fischer, Nachtergaele et al. 2021). These tables provide country and agro-ecological zone-specific irrigation needs for each crop derived using the AquaCrop model (Vanuytrecht, Raes et al. 2014). From the different available parameters, we chose average water demand in Suitable soil conditions. The baseline scenario, same as with the yield, corresponds to historical conditions in time period 1980-2010. Since the yield values range from rainfed to irrigated conditions, the irrigation water use similarly ranges from zero (rainfed) to the above-described irrigation water demand. Life-cycle environmental impacts of potable water production in the EU were taken from the ecoinvent (Wernet, Bauer et al. 2016) database.

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Biomass waste composting

We assume that the plant residues from gardening are composted in domestic composters. We approximate waste biomass production for beans, potatoes, and onions based on equations provided in (De Klein, Novoa et al. 2006). Tomato waste-biomass production is based on (Llorach-Massana, Lopez-Capel et al. 2017), potato residue production is based on (Naik, Narayana et al. 2014), and carrot waste production is based on (Moore, Spring et al. 2021). Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from composting were approximated based on (Nordahl, Preble et al. 2023) for garden waste.

Avoided industrial production

The main expected environmental benefit of gardening is that some part of industrial agricultural production can be avoided. We take two approaches to calculating the avoided impacts. The first is directly assuming that what is produced in the gardens is not produced in the conventional fields. We take the lifecycle environmental impacts of conventional production of the crops (per kg) from the agribalyse and ecoinvent databases (Colomb, Amar et al. 2014) and multiply them by the quantity of vegetables produced in the gardens. As those are avoided impacts, the resulting number is subtracted from the total. The second approach is to take into account the market effects resulting from the drop in demand for the vegetables produced in the garden. For this, we use an agro-economic model, the Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact Modelling System (CAPRI) (Britz and Witzke 2004), described below. The environmental impacts of the resulting changes in agricultural production for EU and non-EU regions are considered using agribalyse and ecoinvent databases.

CAPRI

CAPRI is a partial equilibrium agricultural sector model used for ex-ante analysis and based on microeconomic theory. The global food system is represented, with a focus on the EU agricultural market. The model consists of a global market module and a regional supply module which works in iteration to achieve a market equilibrium. In the global market module, agricultural supply and demand for food, feed and processing industries are represented by a set of behavioral functions. Bilateral trade flows are represented by the Armington assumptions (Armington 1969), i.e., differentiated by commodities and locations. The aim of producers is to maximize profits while utility maximization is assumed for consumers. In the supply module, non-linear programming models represent an average farm whose aim is to maximize profits, respecting constraints such as resources, labor, capital and agricultural policies. The final food

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demand uses a Generalised Leontief functional form, dependent on prices and incomes. CAPRI generates a baseline scenario, representative of a future development pathway considering population, GDP, temperature and precipitation. These are based on past trends, agricultural outlook and expert judgments. More information on the CAPRI methodology is provided in the CAPRI wiki. (https://www.capri-model.org/dokuwiki_help/doku.php)

Avoided lawn maintenance

To evaluate the impacts of gardening consistently, we need to also include avoided lawn maintenance, i.e., mowing of grass which would otherwise grow on the area and composting of the biomass. We quantify the potentially produced grass biomass in the same way as with the vegetables, based on FAO GAEZ data. Similarly as with garden residues, the GHG emissions from composting were approximated based on (Nordahl, Preble et al. 2023). In the baseline scenario, we assume that a petrol-powered lawnmower is used, with petrol consumption between 0.00046 L/m^2 and 0.00078 L/m^2 , which corresponds to values available in the literature (Saidani and Kim (2021) and other resources). Based on the length of the vegetation period and assuming a mowing frequency of approximately two weeks, we assume the number of mows per year at 10 to 17 times per year. The life-cycle environmental impacts of petrol production and burning in machinery are based on ecoinvent database.

Quantification process

For the calculations presented here, we assume 50% of the potential garden area is utilized for gardening, with the rest being left for other leisure activities, trees etc. All the LCA calculations were performed in R (R Core Team 2024). To represent the wide range of gardening practices, regarding what crops are grown, whether fertilizers are applied etc. (as described above), all processes were Monte Carlo simulated. The value for each of the parameters was randomly sampled from the set distribution of values, with 10,000 runs, yielding the final distribution of results. The EF 3.1 (The European Commission 2021) method was used to characterize the environmental impacts into 16 impact categories. Next to the preset distribution of parameters, we also modelled random area share of each crop by randomly sampling from a uniform distribution of 0.05 to 0.5 so that the sum of all crops was always one. Since the GAEZ database provides yield in dry matter mass, we converted it to wet weight based on GAEZ documentation Table 9-1 (Fischer, Nachtergaele et al. 2021). The final balance is calculated as the sum of the environmental impacts of gardening (seeds, irrigation, fertilizers, and biomass waste composting) balances against the avoided impacts of industrial agriculture and avoided lawn

maintenance.

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